

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>RISC-V Coverage by Co-Design</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA10-329</i>
General application	<i>High-reliability ground-level applications</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
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Date(s) of the experiment	<i>From 11-10-2024 to 13-10-2024</i>
Facility	<i>ChipIR</i>
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	<i>48</i>

Objectives of the experiments

In this proposal, we aim to assess detection, recovery, and protection mechanisms in RISC-V cores' full-stack architecture, diverging from traditional designs by integrating reliability and coverage early in development. We focus on including non-functional requirements in both software and hardware from the start, using a cohesive hardware-software co-design strategy. Building on our previous RISC-V core research, this project will delve into architectural insights through low-overhead key modifications. Our methodology includes hardware enhancements and low-level software adjustments, likely incorporating probabilistic data structures and low-overhead software detectors. A crucial part of our experiments involves evaluating coverage against Single Event Upsets (SEUs) in real-time, safety-critical systems, addressing Silent-Data Corruption (SDC) and Detectable Unrecoverable Errors (DUEs) risks. Our co-design approach aims to bolster RISC-V cores' resilience against SEUs, enhancing the reliability of safety-critical systems.

Experiment test report

The experimental setup consisted of 6xSmartFusion 2 Flash FPGAs and 2xSiFive RISC-V microcontroller boards. The FPGAs were used to test multiple hardware implementations of hardware accelerators and detectors, while the RISC-V cores were used to evaluate software routines. A brief description of each experiment follows:

- 1. Testing low-level software detection mechanisms

- 2. Testing multiple AI workloads in low-power microcontrollers
- 3. Validation of probabilistic error detection mechanisms
- 4. Characterization of AI hardware accelerator

Each experiment had multiple configurations to validate different parameters. The measurements from each experiment consisted of performing a specific computation routine with a known result. The output of the computation was transmitted out of the Device Under Test (DUT) via a UART/Ethernet adapter. The validation of the correct result is done entirely in post-processing. The probabilistic error detection mechanism created a ground truth baseline by performing SECDED hamming error detection with the same data. A preliminary overview of the results of each experiment follows:

1. The software routines aimed at validating mechanisms to allow detection of errors by using deeply integrated hardware mechanisms. The results are still being evaluated, but the main objective was to validate if the software could detect Silent Data Corruption errors. It seems that the detection mechanism works to detect errors in computation that still produce an incorrect result (not an error). The biggest drawback of the experiment is that the chosen platform produced a lot of crashes and timeouts, creating noise in the measurements.
2. The data analysis of the AI workloads has not happened yet, they were used as one of the benchmarks for the software detection. The question is if the different models we used have any inherent difference in reliability. If they show any meaningful difference, future campaigns and simulation results will be used to investigate the causes and possible mitigation strategies.
3. The validation of the probabilistic error detection mechanisms has seen the most work. It is the continuation of a previous experiment we performed at ChipIR (published here <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10616084>). The experiments seem to validate that the probabilistic data structures (PDS) work as intended when directly compared with hamming SECDED codes under beam. Contrary to the previous experiments, the PDS was evaluated with a much simpler system, demonstrating that the previous results were probably influenced by other implementation factors. These results have been submitted to a conference and are awaiting peer review.
4. The characterization of the AI HW accelerator will provide a worst-case cross-section estimate, since very few errors were detected. The cross-section of the device is really small, and even with accelerated neutron testing it is difficult to collect enough data for statistical significance. This result validates the idea that such systems would hardly influence the reliability of a system with a large cross-section (such as a microcontroller).

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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